

Risk Factors Associated with Pressure Ulcers among Home Health Care Patients; Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

Dr. Lenah Alaseem ,
Dr. Mohammad Alshehri ,
Dr. Medhat Maher Mohamed ,
Dr. Abdulaziz M. Bin Rsheed ,
Prof. Mostafa Kofi

Family Medicine and Home Health Care Dept., Prince Sultan Military Medical City, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

Abstract

Background: Patients, professionals, and health care systems are faced with a serious problem of pressure ulcers. They represent a significant occurrence and prevalence throughout the world. Their character iatrogenic states that its appearance is preventable, and its incidence is an indicator of scientific and technical quality both in primary care and specialized care. Surgery may be necessary to accelerate the healing process, although most pressure ulcers are usually treated with debridement and conservative therapy. Their reported incidence and prevalence are significant worldwide. **Objectives:** The study's objectives are to identify the pressure ulcer risk factors in patients getting home health care, as well as to look at the quantity, type, and characteristics of pressure ulcers as well as patient comorbidities. **Methods:** Cross-sectional study, Home Care Nursing personnel questionnaire to determine the Risk Factors of Pressure Ulcers, patient comorbidities, and the number, and characteristics of pressure ulcers among patients receiving home care in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. **Results:** PU is prevalent among the studied participants in Saudi Arabia, about 55% of these ulcers showed noticeable distraction of skin and/or deeper soft tissue against a bony prominence. We have also found a significant relationship between PU and gender, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, incontinence issues, nutritional status, and physical status, cerebrovascular accidents, trauma, and chronic kidney disease. **Conclusion:** Different risk factors are associated with PU such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and nutritional, and physical status. To monitor and promote best practices in skin care for highly dependent patients, continued measurement and evaluation of PU incidence, it is recommended more research of risk factors of PU development be assessed at home Health care Centers.

Introduction

Pressure ulcers are common complications that affect at least 10% of patients in acute care, 3% in long-term care and 4% in home care. In spite of advancements in technology and preventive measures, pressure ulcers continue to be a serious global health concern. According to a 2020 study, the prevalence of pressure ulcers was 14.5% in Europe and 12.8% globally between 2008 and 2018. 13.6% in North America, 12.7% in South America, 3% in Asia, 12.6% in the Middle East, and 9% in Australia [1]. The Eastern Mediterranean Region's

pressure ulcer prevalence has ranged from 7% to 44.4% [2]. Injuries caused by pressure ulcers are the third most expensive condition after cancer and cardiovascular diseases, accounting for approximately 4% of the annual health care budget in Europe [3]. For instance, a 2018 US study revealed that individuals with pressure ulcers had costs that were 22.5% greater than those of other patients. [4]. According to clinical definitions, a pressure ulcer occurs when an external pressure source causes the underlying tissues and a specific patch of skin to be destroyed, eventually

More Information

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Keywords:

pressure ulcers,
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resulting in the ischemic area being necrotic [5, 6]. Pressure injuries have a complicated, multifaceted course of development. These ulcers are formed by a combination of internal and external stimuli. External factors that can cause tissue deformation and ischemia include prolonged pressure, friction, shear force, and dampness. Tissue damage might occur more quickly due to internal causes such as endothelial dysfunction, anemia, and starvation [7][8] It is crucial to stress that preventative intervention is the best treatment before going into various pressure ulcer treatment options. Preventive measures include preserving and enhancing tissue tolerance. Maintaining and enhancing tissue tolerance along with appropriate unloading constitute prevention. Pressure dispersion cushions, turning, proper hydration and nourishment, and supportive surfaces could all help achieve this. The skin must be dry and clean [9] Pressure ulcers are less common when turning every 4 hours on a viscoelastic foam mattress or surface than when turning every 2 hours on a regular mattress. Ultimately, the degree of risk, ulcer stage, mobility, patient comfort, and requirement for microclimate management should all be taken into consideration when selecting support surfaces. Hospitals and home health care agencies must implement an evidence-based pressure ulcer prevention program. In the first year of implementation, 150 centers took part in the Bedsore Prevention Program; in the second year, many of these centers experienced a 70% reduction in bedsores, according to a 2008 report from the Association for Bedsore Prevention and the New Jersey Hospital Quality Institute (NJHCQI) [10].

Objectives

To investigate risk Factors associated with Pressure Ulcers, the number and characteristics of pressure ulcers, and patient comorbidities.

Research Design

Cross-sectional study, Home Care Nursing personnel questionnaire to determine the Risk Factors of Pressure Ulcers, the number and characteristics of pressure ulcer and patient comorbidities among patients receiving home care in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

Methods

Study Design

Descriptive Cross sectional – questionnaire-based study.

Target Population

Any male or female, over the age of 60 years old.

Sample Methods and Size

320 participants, participants will be randomly selected. The required sample size is 320 participants from the study population.

Data Collection Form

A questionnaire that contains 12 Questions.

Data Management Plan

- I. Data collection
- II. Inclusion and exclusion
- III. Data analysis
- IV. Data description

Study Population

Patients receiving home health care in Riyadh.

Statistical Methods

All statistical methods done using SPSS.

Study Area

Home health care centers at Prince Sultan military medical city in Riyadh.

Sample Size

320 participants

Data Collection Tools

A structured questionnaire will be handled to nurses in home health care.

Results

Table (1) displays various demographic parameters of the participants. The table presents data on various parameters related to a patient population, including age group distribution, gender, nationality, smoking status, incontinence issues, nutritional status, and the presence of pressure ulcers. The mean age of the individuals in the study is 70.16 years, with a standard deviation of 18. Most patients are aged 71 to 80 or older than 80, comprising 56.7% of the total population. The gender distribution shows a slightly higher representation of males at 54.2%. Notably, all patients in the study are of Saudi nationality. A small percentage of individuals are smokers (8.7%), while a significant proportion experience urine incontinence (75.7%). Fecal incontinence is reported by 47.7% of patients, and poor nutritional status is observed in 30.8% of the population. These findings provide valuable insights into the characteristics and health conditions of the patient cohort under study.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of Participants and Having Pressure ulcer/s (n=321)

Parameter		No.	Percent
Age group <u>(Mean age is 70.16 years ± 18)</u>	Less than 50	43	13.4
	50 to 60	27	8.4
	61 to 70	69	21.5
	71 to 80	85	26.5
	Older than 80	97	30.2
Gender	Male	174	54.2
	Female	147	45.8
Nationality	Saudi	321	100.0
	Non-Saudi	0	0
Smoker	Yes	28	8.7
	No	293	91.3
urine incontinence	Yes	243	75.7
	No	78	24.3
fecal incontinence	No	168	52.3
	Yes	153	47.7
nutritional status	Proper	222	69.2
	Poor	99	30.8
Does the patient have pressure ulcer/s	Yes	307	95.6
	No	14	4.4

As illustrated in table (2), it is evident that most patients included in the study exhibit a single pressure ulcer, accounting for 81.1% of the cases. The most common description of the pressure ulcer is a noticeable destruction of the skin and/or deeper soft tissue against a bony prominence, representing 55% of the cases. Furthermore, a significant proportion of patients are immobile or bedridden (88.9%), have no history of

diabetes mellitus (44%), and have a history of hypertension (36.5%). It is notable that a considerable portion of patients have chronic kidney disease (16.6%), while a smaller percentage have a history of trauma or injury (7.5%). These findings shed light on the prevalence of pressure ulcers and associated medical conditions within the patient population under investigation.

Table 2: Number of Ulcers and Related Risk Factors among Patients with Ulcers (n=307)

Parameter		No.	Percent
Number of pressure ulcers the patient has	One	249	81.1
	2	20	6.5
	3	23	7.5
	4	9	2.9
	5 or more	6	2.0
Description of the pressure ulcer/s	Localized area of necrosis	77	25.1
	Noticeable distraction of skin and/or deeper soft tissue against a bony prominence	169	55.0
	Both	40	13.0
	Not mentioned	21	6.8
Patient's physical condition	Active	34	11.1
	Immobile/Bedridden	273	88.9
Diabetes mellitus	No	172	56.0
	Yes	135	44.0
Hypertension	No	195	63.5
	Yes	112	36.5
Cerebrovascular accidents	No	198	64.5
	Yes	109	35.5
History of trauma or injury	No	284	92.5
	Yes	23	7.5
Chronic kidney disease	No	256	83.4
	Yes	51	16.6

Figure 1: Shows Description of the Ulcers among Participants with Ulcers (n=307)

Table 3: It shows that there’s a significant relation between having pressure ulcers and gender, diabetes mellitus, and hypertension, while it shows relationship

between smoking, incontinence issues, nutrition and physical status, cerebrovascular accidents, trauma, and chronic kidney disease.

Table 3: Shows Relation between Pressure Ulcers and Various Risk Factors

		Pressure ulcer/s among the patients		Total (N=321)
		Yes (307)	No (14)	
Age group (in years)	50 to 60	27 8.8%	0 0.0%	27 8.4%
	61 to 70	66 21.5%	3 21.4%	69 21.5%
	71 to 80	80 26.1%	5 35.7%	85 26.5%
	Less than 50	43 14.0%	0 0.0%	43 13.4%
	Older than 80	91 29.6%	6 42.9%	97 30.2%
Gender	Male	170 55.4%	4 28.6%	174 54.2%
	Female	137 44.6%	10 71.4%	147 45.8%
Smoking status	Smoker	27 8.8%	1 7.1%	28 8.7%
	Non-smoker	280 91.2%	13 92.9%	293 91.3%
Urinary incontinence	Yes	232 75.6%	11 78.6%	243 75.7%
	No	75 24.4%	3 21.4%	78 24.3%
Fecal incontinence	Yes	144 46.9%	9 64.3%	153 47.7%
	No	163 53.1%	5 35.7%	168 52.3%

Nutritional status	Poor	97	2	99
		31.6%	14.3%	30.8%
	Proper	210	12	222
		68.4%	85.7%	69.2%
Physical status	Active	34	2	36
		11.1%	14.3%	11.2%
	Immobile/Bedridden	273	12	285
		88.9%	85.7%	88.8%
Diabetes mellitus	No	172	3	175
		56.0%	21.4%	54.5%
	Yes	135	11	146
		44.0%	78.6%	45.5%
Hypertension	No	195	3	198
		63.5%	21.4%	61.7%
	Yes	112	11	123
		36.5%	78.6%	38.3%
Cerebrovascular accidents	No	198	10	208
		64.5%	71.4%	64.8%
	Yes	109	4	113
		35.5%	28.6%	35.2%
Trauma/injury	No	284	12	296
		92.5%	85.7%	92.2%
	Yes	23	2	25
		7.5%	14.3%	7.8%
Chronic kidney disease	No	256	12	268
		83.4%	85.7%	83.5%
	Yes	51	2	53
		16.6%	14.3%	16.5%

Table (4) Shows frequency and proportions in relation to having localized areas of necrosis and gender, fecal incontinence, and cerebrovascular accidents. On the other hand, also between age groups, smoking, urinary

incontinence, nutritional status, physical status, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, trauma/injury, and chronic kidney disease.

Table 4: Relation between Having Localized Areas of Necrosis and Different Risk Factors among the Participants (n=321)

		Having localized area/s of necrosis		Total (N=321)
		Yes (117)	No (204)	
Age group (in years)	50 to 60	14	13	27
		12.0%	6.4%	8.4%
	61 to 70	25	44	69
		21.4%	21.6%	21.5%
	71 to 80	33	52	85
		28.2%	25.5%	26.5%
Less than 50	13	30	43	
	11.1%	14.7%	13.4%	
Older than 80	32	65	97	
	27.4%	31.9%	30.2%	
Gender	Male	71	103	174
		60.7%	50.5%	54.2%
	Female	46	101	147
		39.3%	49.5%	45.8%
Smoking status	Smoker	8	20	28

		6.8%	9.8%	8.7%	
	Non-smoker	109	184	293	
		93.2%	90.2%	91.3%	
Urinary incontinence	Yes	92	151	243	
		78.6%	74.0%	75.7%	
No		25	53	78	
		21.4%	26.0%	24.3%	
Fecal incontinence	Yes	40	113	153	
		34.2%	55.4%	47.7%	
No		77	91	168	
		65.8%	44.6%	52.3%	
Nutritional status	Poor	43	56	99	
		36.8%	27.5%	30.8%	
Proper		74	148	222	
		63.2%	72.5%	69.2%	
Physical status	Active	13	23	36	
		11.1%	11.3%	11.2%	
Immobile/Bedridden		104	181	285	
		88.9%	88.7%	88.8%	
Diabetes mellitus	No	69	106	175	
		59.0%	52.0%	54.5%	
Yes		48	98	146	
		41.0%	48.0%	45.5%	
Hypertension	No	74	124	198	
		63.2%	60.8%	61.7%	
Yes		43	80	123	
		36.8%	39.2%	38.3%	
Cerebrovascular accidents	No	65	143	208	
		55.6%	70.1%	64.8%	
Yes		52	61	113	
		44.4%	29.9%	35.2%	
Trauma/injury	No	108	188	296	
		92.3%	92.2%	92.2%	
Yes		9	16	25	
		7.7%	7.8%	7.8%	
Chronic kidney disease	No	94	174	268	
		80.3%	85.3%	83.5%	
Yes		23	30	53	
		19.7%	14.7%	16.5%	

Table (5) It shows the frequency and distribution of noticeable distractions of skin and/or deeper soft tissue against bony prominence and incontinence issues, nutritional, and physical status. On the other hand, it

shows frequency distribution and proportions between age groups, gender, smoking, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, trauma/injury, cerebrovascular accidents, and chronic kidney disease.

Table 5: Relation between Having Noticeable Tissue Distraction against a Bony Prominence and Different Risk Factors among the Participants (n=321)

		Having noticeable distraction of skin and/or deeper soft tissue against a bony prominence		Total (N=321)	
		Yes (209)	No (112)		
Age group (in years)	50 to 60	18	9	27	
		8.6%	8.0%	8.4%	

	61 to 70	43	26	69
		20.6%	23.2%	21.5%
	71 to 80	51	34	85
		24.4%	30.4%	26.5%
	Less than 50	34	9	43
		16.3%	8.0%	13.4%
	Older than 80	63	34	97
		30.1%	30.4%	30.2%
Gender	Male	117	57	174
		56.0%	50.9%	54.2%
	Female	92	55	147
		44.0%	49.1%	45.8%
Smoking status	Smoker	18	10	28
		8.6%	8.9%	8.7%
	Non-smoker	191	102	293
		91.4%	91.1%	91.3%
Urinary incontinence	Yes	166	77	243
		79.4%	68.8%	75.7%
	No	43	35	78
		20.6%	31.3%	24.3%
Fecal incontinence	Yes	109	44	153
		52.2%	39.3%	47.7%
	No	100	68	168
		47.8%	60.7%	52.3%
Nutritional status	Poor	73	26	99
		34.9%	23.2%	30.8%
	Proper	136	86	222
		65.1%	76.8%	69.2%
Physical status	Active	15	21	36
		7.2%	18.8%	11.2%
	Immobile/Bedridden	194	91	285
		92.8%	81.3%	88.8%
Diabetes mellitus	No	119	56	175
		56.9%	50.0%	54.5%
	Yes	90	56	146
		43.1%	50.0%	45.5%
Hypertension	No	135	63	198
		64.6%	56.3%	61.7%
	Yes	74	49	123
		35.4%	43.8%	38.3%
Cerebrovascular accidents	No	132	76	208
		63.2%	67.9%	64.8%
	Yes	77	36	113
		36.8%	32.1%	35.2%
Trauma/injury	No	192	104	296
		91.9%	92.9%	92.2%
	Yes	17	8	25
		8.1%	7.1%	7.8%
Chronic kidney disease	No	179	89	268
		85.6%	79.5%	83.5%
	Yes	30	23	53
		14.4%	20.5%	16.5%

Discussion

A variety of clinical and social services are offered by qualified professionals to patients in their homes as part of the home health care (HHC) program. [11, 12] The main pillars of HHC programs are nursing care and basic medical assessment. Most people who use HHC services are elderly, frail, or suffering from a disability or functional decline. Home care (HC) services can be provided for a variety of lengths of time, from shorter periods of time, such as after surgery, to long-term, chronic nursing care. Whatever the nature, environment, or characteristics of the recipient, most HHC programs have the same objective of offering clinical treatment to enhance the patient's quality of life and lower hospitalization rates. [13, 14] Pressure ulcers (PUs) are one of the most common problems faced globally in health care settings [15, 16]. PUs has an impact on the rising health care costs and on the patient's health because of the increase in both morbidity and mortality. In the quest to enhance patient outcomes, research on the development of PUs has drawn more attention. Since pressure ulcers (PUs) are a predictable and preventable phenomenon, this consequence is one of the most important indicators of nursing care quality and patient safety in the healthcare setting. [17,18]. PU prevalence data vary widely across both settings and country. One Saudi Arabian (SA) study [19] Reported acute care PU prevalence of 44.4% and incidence of 38.6%. Identifying patients at risk for PU development is essential for the effective implementation of PU prevention programs and usage of resources. Tayyib *et al.* [20] Ascertained 28 factors associated with accelerated PU development in critically ill patients; Nonetheless, the most often mentioned risk factors included advanced age, prolonged ICU stays, a history of diabetes and cardiovascular disease, and infrequent repositioning. In our study we aimed to detect the Risk Factors of Pressure Ulcers, number and characteristics of pressure ulcer and patient comorbidities among patients receiving home health care.

A study in an elderly care home in Japan showed that more than 91% of the total study population had a pressure ulcer at various intensities. [21] On the other hand, Rodriques and Megie [22] discovered that pressure ulcers accounted for 37% of wounds in patients receiving home health care, with an average wound length of almost 27 months. One study found that only 27% of patients with existing pressure ulcers and 14% of those at risk were receiving the proper pressure-reducing treatment. Approximately 1 in 10 patients admitted to a home health care facility had pressure ulcers, and approximately one-third were at risk of developing new ulcers. [23] As regards the relation between pressure ulcers and various risk factors, there's a significant relation between having

pressure ulcers and gender, diabetes mellitus, and hypertension, while it shows insignificant relation with smoking, incontinence issues, nutritional and physical status, cerebrovascular accidents, trauma, and chronic kidney disease. On the other hand, different studies revealed that incontinence, mobility impairment, skin drainage, recent fractures, nutritional, physical status, and anemia were associated with pressure ulcer development. [24, 25], which is inconsistent with our results. There is also accumulating evidence suggesting that malnutrition has been associated with pressure ulcer development and its severity because of its negative impact on wound healing. [26] Moreover, the multivariate analyzes of Nassaji *et al.* And Slowikowski and Funk [27] identified diabetes as being significantly associated with the appearance of PUs (OR [95%CI]=5.58 [1.83–18.70] and OR [95%CI]=1.93 [1.11–3.35], respectively). Another study [28] observed significance for this parameter in the univariate analysis. Renal failure was assessed as a potential risk factor in two studies. Only the study of O'Brien *et al.*, [29] found renal failure to be significantly associated with the appearance of PUs in the multivariate analysis (OR [95%CI]=1.75 [1.27–2.39]). Another study revealed that Fecal incontinence is associated with the appearance of PUs [31] (OR [95%CI]=3.42 [1.45–8.06]). In contrast to our results, Tannen and Dassen reported that age and trauma/injury are the most important factors contributing to the incidence of pressure ulcers [30] Hoshowsky and Schramm [31] state that patients who are aged above 40 years were at high risk for PU development. This contrasts with studies that demonstrate that age is not a predisposing factor for PU development [32, 33]. As regards description of the ulcers among participants, we have found that about 55% had noticeable distraction of skin and/or deeper soft tissue against a bony prominence, and about 25% had localized areas of necrosis. The type of PU with noticeable distraction of skin showed a significant association with incontinence issues, nutrition, and physical status, while localized area of necrosis showed a significant association with gender, fecal incontinence, and cerebrovascular accidents.[34]. Afterall, The goal of home healthcare providers is to deliver safe, effective treatment while respecting the autonomy of each patient and considering the unique features of their family and home.

Conclusion

Different risk factors are associated with PU gender, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, smoking, incontinence issues, nutrition and physical status, cerebrovascular accidents, trauma, and chronic kidney disease. Moreover, there is a need for continued research on the measurement and evaluation of PU risk factors for development are recommended in Saudi Arabia health

care centers to monitor and promote best practices in skin care for highly dependent patients.

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References

- [1] Li Z, Lin F, Thalib L, Chaboyer W. Global prevalence and incidence of pressure injuries in hospitalised adult patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J Nurs Stud.* 2020;1(105):103546. doi: 10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2020.103546.
- [2] Tayyib N, Coyer F, Lewis P. Saudi Arabian adult intensive care unit pressure ulcer incidence and risk factors: a prospective cohort study. *Int Wound J.* 2016;13(5):912–919. doi: 10.1111/iwj.12406
- [3] Lin F, Wu Z, Song B, Coyer F, Chaboyer W. The effectiveness of multicomponent pressure injury prevention programs in adult intensive care patients: a systematic review. *Int J Nurs Stud.* 2020;1(102):103483. doi: 10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2019.103483
- [4] Guest JF, Fuller GW, Vowden P, Vowden KR. Cohort study evaluating pressure ulcer management in clinical practice in the UK following initial presentation in the community: costs and outcomes. *BMJ Open.* 2018;8(7):e021769. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2018-021769
- [5] Bouten CV, Oomens CW, Baaijens FP, Bader DL. The etiology of pressure ulcers: skin deep or muscle bound? *Archives of physical medicine and rehabilitation.* 2003;84(4):616–9.
- [6] Berlowitz DR, Brienza DM. Are all pressure ulcers the result of deep tissue injury? A review of the literature. *Ostomy/wound managemen.* 2007;53(10):34–8.
- [7] Anders J, Heinemann A, Leffmann C, Leutenegger M, Pröfener F, von Renteln-Kruse W. Decubitus ulcers: pathophysiology and primary prevention. *Dtsch Arztebl Int.* 2010 May;107(21):371–81; quiz 382.
- [8] Bansal C, Scott R, Stewart D, Cockerell CJ. Decubitus ulcers: a review of the literature. *Int J Dermatol.* 2005 Oct;44(10):805–10.
- [9] Tannen A, Dassen T, Bours G, Halfens R. A comparison of pressure ulcer prevalence: concerted data collection in the Netherlands and Germany. *Int J Nurs Stud.* 2004;41(6):607–612. doi: 10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2004.01.005
- [10] Mosadeghrad AM. Occupational stress and its consequences: Implications for health policy and management. *Leadersh Health Serv J.* 2014;27(3):224–239. doi: 10.1108/LHS-07-2013-0032
- [11] Burton JK, Wolters AT, Towers AM, et al. Developing a minimum data set for older adult care homes in the UK: exploring the concept and defining early core principles. *Lancet Healthy Longev.* 2022;3(3):e186–e193. doi: 10.1016/S2666-7568(22)00010-1
- [12] Walters K, Frost R, Kharicha K, et al. Home-based health promotion for older people with mild frailty: the HomeHealth intervention development and feasibility RCT. *Health Technol Assess (Rockv).* 2017;21(73):1–128. doi: 10.3310/hta21730
- [13] O'Connor M. Hospitalization Among Medicare-Reimbursed Skilled Home Health Recipients. *Home Health Care Manag Pract.* 2012;24(1):27–37. doi: 10.1177/1084822311419498
- [14] Feuchtinger J, Halfens R, Dassen T. Pressure ulcer risk assessment immediately after cardiac surgery – does it make a difference? A comparison of three pressure ulcer risk assessment instruments within a cardiac surgery population. *Nurs Crit Care* 2007;12:42–9.
- [15] Nijs N, Toppets A, Defloor T, Bernaerts K, Milisen K, Van Den Berghe G. Incidence and risk factors for pressure ulcers in the intensive care unit. *J Clin Nurs* 2009;18:1258–66.
- [16] Shahin ESM, Dassen T, Halfens RJG. Pressure ulcer prevalence and incidence in intensive care patients: a literature review. *Nurs Crit Care* 2008;13:71–9.
- [17] Aydin CE, Bolton LB, Donaldson N, Brown DS, Buffum M, Elashoff JD, Sandhu M. Creating and analyzing a statewide nursing quality measurement database. *J Nurs Scholarsh* 2004;36:371–8.
- [18] Tayyib N, Coyer F, Lewis P. Pressure ulcers in the adult intensive care unit: a literature review of patient risk factors and risk assessment scales. *J Nurs Educ Pract* 2013;3:28–42.
- [19] Saleh M. The impact of pressure ulcer risk assessment on patient outcomes among hospitalised patients at Riyadh Military Hospital – Saudi Arabia. Leicester: De Montfort University, 2007. [
- [20] Tayyib N, Coyer F, Lewis P. Pressure ulcers in the adult intensive care unit: a literature review of patient risk factors and risk assessment scales. *J Nurs Educ Pract* 2013;3:28–42.
- [21] Donnelly J, Winder J, Kernohan W, Stevenson M. An RCT to determine the effect of a heel elevation device in pressure ulcer prevention post-hip fracture. *J Wound Care.* 2011;20:309–18.

- [22] Rodrigues I, Megie MF. Prevalence of chronic wounds in Quebec home care: an exploratory study. *Ostomy Wound Manage* . 2006 May;52(5):46–8. 50, 52–7.
- [23] Ferrell BA, Josephson K, Norvid P, et al. Pressure ulcers among patients admitted to home health care. *J Am Geriatr Soc*. 2000;48(9):1042–7.
- [24] Bergquist S. Subscales, subscores, or summative score: evaluating the contribution of Braden Scale items for predicting pressure ulcer risk in older adults receiving home health care. *J Wound Ostomy Continence Nurs*. 2001;28(6):279–89.
- [25] Iizaka S, Okuwa M, Sugama J, Sanada H. The impact of malnutrition and nutrition-related factors on the development and severity of pressure ulcers in older patients receiving home care. *Clinical Nutrition*. 2010;29(1):47–53.
- [26] Nassaji M, Askari Z, Ghorbani R. Cigarette smoking and risk of pressure ulcer in adult intensive care unit patients. *Int J Nurs Pract*. 2014 Aug;20(4):418-23. doi: 10.1111/ijn.12141
- [27] O'Brien DD, Shanks AM, Talsma A, Brenner PS, Ramachandran SK. Intraoperative risk factors associated with postoperative pressure ulcers in critically ill patients: a retrospective observational study. *Crit Care Med*. 2014 Jan;42(1):40-7. doi: 10.1097/CCM.0b013e318298a849
- [28] Slowikowski GC, Funk M. Factors associated with pressure ulcers in patients in a surgical intensive care unit. *J Wound Ostomy Continence Nurs*. 2010 Nov-Dec;37(6):619-26. doi: 10.1097/WON.0b013e3181f90a34
- [29] Mosadeghrad AM. Occupational stress and its consequences: Implications for health policy and management. *Leadersh Health Serv J*. 2014;27(3):224–239. doi: 10.1108/LHS-07-2013-0032
- [30] Hoshowsky VM, Schramm CA. Intraoperative pressure sore prevention: an analysis of bedding materials. *Res Nurs Health* 1994;17:333–9.
- [31] Sayar S, Turgut S, Doğan H, Ekici A, Yurtsever S, Demirkan F, Doruk N, Taşdelen B. Incidence of pressure ulcers in intensive care unit patients at risk according to the Waterlow scale and factors influencing the development of pressure ulcers. *J Clin Nurs* 2009;18:765–74.
- [32] Theaker C, Kuper M, Soni N. Pressure ulcer prevention in intensive care – a randomised control trial of two pressure-relieving devices. *Anaesthesia* 2005;60:395–9.
- [33] Nixon J, Brown J, McElvenny D, Mason S, Bond S. Prognostic factors associated with pressure sore development in the immediate post-operative period. *Int J Nurs Stud* 2000;37:279–89.
- [34] Awoke N, Tekalign T, Arba A, Lenjebo TL. Pressure injury prevention practice and associated factors among nurses at Wolaita Sodo University Teaching and Referral Hospital, South Ethiopia: a cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open*. 2022 Mar 14;12(3):e047687. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2020-047687

